

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MATHEMATICAL GAME-BASED LEARNING ACTIVITIES: BASIS FOR CONTEXTUALIZED TEACHING STRATEGY PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities (MGBLA) in enhancing engagement, understanding, and mastery in elementary mathematics education. It involved 245 learner respondents and 23 teacher respondents from 19 schools in the North District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan for the academic year 2024-2025. Data were analyzed using frequency distribution, percentage distribution, and weighted mean. The study found that both learners and teachers perceived MGBLA as very effective tools for improving engagement, understanding, and mastery. Despite these positive perceptions, several challenges were identified, including difficulties in curriculum integration, technological competence, and teacher training. The findings also revealed that learners had access to mathematical manipulatives, but digital tools like cellphones, internet, and laptops were less accessible. Additionally, there was a significant relationship between the effectiveness of MGBLA and the challenges faced by teachers. Based on these findings, the study recommends integrating game-based strategies into the official curriculum, providing adequate resources and training for teachers, and using contextualized teaching strategies to enhance the effectiveness of MGBLA.

Keywords: *Mathematical Game-Based Learning, Mathematical Manipulatives, Engagement, Digital Learning Tools, Curriculum Integration*

INTRODUCTION

Elementary Mathematics Education is essential in building foundational skills for learners, particularly in numeracy, which supports advanced learning. However, Mathematics is often seen as uninteresting, difficult, and boring. Recently, integrating games in elementary education, especially for teaching Mathematics, has gained popularity. With the rise of digital technology, teachers are exploring innovative ways to make learning more engaging. Digital games, which involve problem-solving tasks, immediate feedback, and puzzles, are effective in making mathematical concepts more accessible and enjoyable. Manipulatives also play a crucial role by helping learners understand abstract concepts in a concrete manner. Cooperative learning further supports the process, fostering active participation and engagement in learning.

Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities, combining games and manipulatives, offer a unique space for individual participation, enhancing conceptual understanding and retention. Studies have proven the effectiveness of these activities in motivating students, improving critical thinking, and sustaining interest. Games provide a competitive yet fun atmosphere that promotes interaction among students.

In the Philippines, studies like that of Libradilla et al. (2015) highlight the appeal of game-based lessons, especially with the use of computers, though challenges like the lack of digital resources persist. However, the Department of Education has made efforts to equip schools with digital tools, such as computers and tablets. In the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, training in integrating interactive games like Kahoot has been conducted, promoting an engaging, collaborative, and competitive learning environment. The researcher's observations show improvements in student performance when using digital games, manipulatives, and cooperative learning strategies.

Ultimately, Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities play a vital role in enhancing engagement, understanding, and mastery in Mathematics, and the researcher aims to assess their effectiveness in the North District of Ilagan.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities as basis for Contextualized Teaching Strategy Plan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - A. Learner Respondents
 - a. Type of school
 - b. Available Learning Resources
 - B. Teacher Respondents
 - a. Type of School
 - b. Level of Recent Related Training Attended
 - c. Educational Qualifications
 - d. Teaching Position

2. How effective are the Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities as perceived by the respondents in terms of Engagement, Understanding, and Mastery?
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents on the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities?
4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents when grouped according to profile?
5. How serious are the challenges encountered by the teachers on the use of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities?
6. Is there a significant difference on the challenges encountered by teachers when grouped according to profile?
7. How does the perceived effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities relate to the challenges encountered by the teacher respondents?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study of The Effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity: Basis for Contextualized Teaching Strategy Plan used the descriptive survey method of research. The method helps the researcher explain the nature of situations based on conditions and information acquired. In this support, Good and Scates (1972) emphasized that the descriptive method is often characterized as a survey or nominative approach as it is used to look for insights into factors or conditions that are prevailing or existing.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in the North District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, which is under the supervision of the Department of Education. The North District is one of the six educational districts within the division and is geographically located in the northern portion of the City of Ilagan, Isabela.

The district comprises several public elementary and secondary schools that cater to a diverse population of learners from both rural and semi-urban communities. These schools vary in size and resources but are united by the common goal of delivering quality basic education.

The North District plays a significant role in the educational framework of the city by providing equitable access to education and supporting DepEd's mission of ensuring inclusive, accessible, and quality learning for every Filipino child. Its schools serve as the setting for this research, particularly focusing on Grade 6 learners and teachers who are directly engaged in implementing innovative teaching strategies such as mathematical game-based learning.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Grade 6 learners and Grade 6 teachers of the 17 Elementary Schools and 2 Integrated Schools in the North District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan who are currently enrolled in the Academic Year 2024-2025. A total of 245 learners were randomly selected from the total population of 617 learners in the North District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. This method guarantees equal representation for all learners while preserving randomness in the selection process. Additionally, a total population of 23 grade 6 teachers are also the respondents of this study.

The table below shows the distribution of the respondents with their respective schools:

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Name of School	Number of Learner Respondents	Number of Teacher Respondents
1. Sta. Catalina Elementary School	7	1
2. Rang-Ayan Elementary School	17	1
3. Fuyo Elementary School	10	1
4. Sta. Victoria Elementary School	13	1
5. Nanagan Elementary School	4	1
6. Capellan Elementary School	33	2
7. Minabang Elementary School	9	1
8. Tangcul-San Isidro Elementary School	24	2
9. Morado Elementary School	9	1
10. Pasa Elementary School	14	1
11. Bangag Elementary School	13	1
12. Capo Elementary School	8	1
13. San Pablo-Quimalabasa Elementary School	5	1
14. San Lorenzo Integrated School	11	1
15. Balla Elementary School	7	1
16. San Rodrigo Elementary School	7	1
17. San Juan-Rugao Elementary School	27	2
18. Marana 3 rd Elementary School	4	1
19. Manaring Integrated School	23	2
Total	245	23

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission to conduct the study in the selected schools in the Ilagan North District were requested from the Schools Division Superintendent and from the District-in-Charge

of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, Isabela. Following the approval, the researcher discussed with the principals of the above-mentioned schools the procedures and processes on the conduct of the study. As the study progressed, the researcher personally discussed the purpose and objectives of the survey with the respondents to ensure the confidentiality of personal data. After administering and retrieving the questionnaire from the respondents, the data were tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used in the study:

Weighted Mean. This was used to determine the level of effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities in terms of engagement, understanding, and mastery.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used to analyze the respondent's profile.

Frequency and Rank. This was employed to analyze and rank the availability of learning materials of the learner respondents.

F-test. This was used to determine the significant difference in engagement, understanding, and mastery of respondents when grouped according to profile in the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities.

Pearson's R. This was used to determine the relationship of the teachers' perception on the effectiveness and challenges encountered on the use of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the respondents in relation to the following variables?

A. Learner Respondents

1) Type of School

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Learner Respondents According to Type of School

Type of School	Frequency	Percentage
Small	127	52
Medium	84	34
Large	34	14
Total	245	100

Table 2 presents the profile of the learner respondents according to the type of school. Most of the respondents, 127 or 52%, come from small schools, indicating that small schools make up the majority of the sample population. Medium-sized schools account for 84 or 34%, while large schools represent the smallest share at 34 or 13%. This data reflects that most learner respondents are from small schools, which aligns with the fact that 14 out of the 19 participating schools in the North District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan are categorized as small. This finding is supported by DepEd Order No. 40, s. 2014, which mandates that there should be at least one elementary school for every barangay. In the North District, every barangay has its own elementary school, and most of these schools are considered small as they do not meet the standard class size of 35 learners for Grades 4 to 6, as set by the Department of Education.

2) Available Learning Resources

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Learner Respondents According to Available Learning Resources

Available Learning Resources	Frequency	Rank
Mathematical Manipulatives	245	1
Cellphone/Tablet	137	2
Internet	137	2
Laptop	25	3

The table presents the availability of learning resources among respondents. Mathematical manipulatives were the most widely available, with 245 respondents reporting access, making them the most commonly used resource in the learning environment. Access to cellphones/tablets and the internet was reported by 137 respondents, ranking second, indicating that these digital tools are often used interchangeably for learning, especially in digital or game-based settings. However, only 25 respondents had access to laptops, suggesting a significant limitation in the availability of advanced digital learning devices. The widespread distribution of mathematical manipulatives by the Department of Education contrasts with the uneven access to digital tools like laptops, cellphones, and the internet. This discrepancy challenges the idea proposed by Dichev & Dichev (2017) that nearly all learners can afford tablets or laptops for game-based learning, as the data reveals that not all learners have access to such devices, particularly laptops.

B. Teacher Respondents
1) Type of School

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher Respondents According to Type of School

Type of School	Frequency	Percentage
Small	14	61
Medium	6	26
Large	3	13
Total	23	100

The table reveals the profile of the teacher respondents according to type of school. As revealed in the data above, most of the respondents, 14 individuals (61percent), are from Small Schools, indicating that smaller schools are more represented in the data. 6 respondents (26percent) come from Medium Schools, reflecting a moderate level of representation. The least number of respondents, 3 individuals (13percent), are from Large Schools, showing that these institutions are underrepresented in the sample. The data reveals that teacher respondents from small schools were the most numbered in the study, primarily because most of the participating schools in the North District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan are classified as small. Specifically, 14 out of the 19 participating schools fall under this category.

2) Level of Related Training Attended

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher Respondents According to Level of Related Training Attended

Level of Related Training Attended	Frequency	Percentage
School	23	100
District	23	100
Division	23	100
Regional	0	0
National	0	0

The table shows that 100% of respondents attended training at the School, District, and Division Levels. This reflects full participation in training or programs at these levels, indicating that such events are either mandatory, highly accessible, or strongly supported. It also suggests effective communication and implementation of initiatives at the division level. This finding aligns with the study by Navarro et al. (2016), which supports the idea that training enhances both teacher performance and student learning outcomes. The

study emphasizes the role of training frameworks in educational institutions to improve teachers' skills and, consequently, the learning process.

3) Educational Qualifications

Table 6
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher Respondents According to Educational Qualifications

Educational Qualifications	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	0	0
Masteral with Units	13	57
Master's Graduate	7	30
Doctoral with Units	2	9
Doctorate Graduate	1	4
Total	23	100

The table presents the educational qualifications of teacher respondents. The majority, comprising 13 respondents (57%), have earned academic units towards a master's degree but have not completed the program. Seven respondents (30%) have successfully obtained a master's degree, while two respondents (9%) have earned units at the doctoral level. Only one respondent holds a completed doctoral degree. The data indicates that most respondents have pursued education beyond the bachelor's degree, with a smaller number completing their graduate programs, particularly at the doctoral level. Many teachers pursue advanced degrees as a means to advance in their careers, as promotions are based on a points system that rewards higher qualifications. UNESCO (2020) highlights the importance of advanced education for teachers to adapt to evolving curricula, technology, and learners' needs. However, the system may sometimes overlook teachers with extensive classroom experience but only a bachelor's degree.

4) Teaching Position

Table 7
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher Respondents According to Teaching Position

Teaching Position	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	0	0
Teacher II	0	0
Teacher III	20	87
Master Teacher I	3	13
Master Teacher II	0	0
Total	23	100

The table presents the teaching positions of the respondents. Most respondents, specifically 20 (87%), hold the position of Teacher III, indicating that they are in mid-level roles within the teaching career. Meanwhile, 3 respondents (13%) are Master Teacher I, signifying a higher rank. The data shows that most respondents are mid-career professionals, with a smaller portion having advanced to higher ranks, highlighting the potential for professional growth. To facilitate advancement, support mechanisms such as mentoring, advanced studies, or training are needed. Additionally, there are no Teacher I positions due to reclassification; Teacher I positions have been upgraded to Teacher II or III as per DO 7, s. 2007 (Department of Education, 2007), based on qualifications, experience, and accomplishments.

2. How effective are the Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities as perceived by the respondents in terms of Engagement, Understanding, and Mastery?

Table 8
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Digital Games as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Engagement

Statements	Kahoot		Quizziz		Wordwall		Interactive Games		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. My learners/I enjoy doing activities with the use of mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.87	3.84	3.76	3.62	3.33	3.35	3.58	3.47	3.60	Very Effective
2. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to learn.	3.82	3.87	3.72	3.69	3.29	3.27	3.67	3.61	3.62	Very Effective
3. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to attend a class every day.	3.78	3.89	3.70	3.73	3.06	3.11	3.64	3.73	3.58	Very Effective
4. My learners/I like playing mathematical game-based learning activities in class.	3.67	3.76	3.73	3.74	2.84	3.08	3.58	3.73	3.52	Very Effective
5. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to explore mathematics more.	3.47	3.64	3.72	3.69	3.00	3.08	3.51	3.78	3.49	Very Effective
6. Mathematical game-based learning activities make my learners/me	3.57	3.68	3.69	3.74	2.89	3.00	3.57	3.73	3.48	Very Effective

attentive and participative in class.											
7. Using mathematical game-based learning activities seems interesting to my learners/me.	3.58	3.68	3.74	3.78	3.05	3.14	3.62	3.67	3.53	Very Effective	
8. My learners/I enjoy playing mathematical game-based learning activities in class and at the same time my learners/I also learn.	3.68	3.76	3.70	3.73	3.13	3.16	3.69	3.83	3.59	Very Effective	
9. Mathematical game-based learning activities provided my learners/me to participate in the lesson.	3.80	3.83	3.73	3.69	3.25	3.33	3.69	3.49	3.60	Very Effective	
10. Mathematical game-based learning activities increased my learner's/my interest in the lesson.	3.84	3.85	3.76	3.63	3.26	3.32	3.72	3.51	3.61	Very Effective	
Overall Mean	Teacher						3.54		Very Effective		
	Learner						3.58		Very Effective		

Table 8 presents the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of digital games as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under engagement. The overall mean rating from teachers is 3.54, and from learners, 3.58, both categorized as "Very Effective." Kahoot and Quizziz received the highest ratings, indicating they are the most favored platforms, while Wordwall received the lowest scores, particularly from teachers, suggesting it may be less engaging. Learners expressed high enjoyment and motivation, particularly in increased attendance and lesson interest. While Wordwall received lower ratings, it was still considered "Very Effective." These findings align with studies by Balaskas et al. (2023), Jarrah et al. (2025), and Capuno (2022), supporting the effectiveness of Kahoot and Quizizz in enhancing engagement, motivation, and academic achievement. Despite its lower engagement, Wordwall was noted to improve understanding of mathematical concepts (Muhammad & Lestari, 2023). Overall, game-based tools like Kahoot, Quizizz, and Wordwall were deemed effective in engaging learners in mathematics.

Table 9
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Digital Games as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Understanding

Statements	Kahoot		Quizziz		Wordwall		Interactive Games		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. Mathematical game-based learning	3.87	3.89	3.92	3.86	3.23	3.33	3.56	3.41	3.63	Very Effective

activities help my learners/me easily understand some parts of the lesson.										
2. My learners/I think mathematical game-based learning activities are important and useful for better learning.	3.78	3.84	3.76	3.78	3.04	3.16	3.47	3.78	3.58	Very Effective
3. My learners/I learn in mathematics because of mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.77	3.64	3.84	3.65	2.88	3.11	3.39	3.42	3.46	Very Effective
4. Mathematical game-based learning activities help my learners/me to enhance their/my social skills.	3.81	3.78	3.78	3.71	2.56	2.82	3.44	3.46	3.42	Very Effective
5. My learners/I learn mathematics concepts easily because of mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.88	3.87	3.85	3.77	2.60	2.95	3.42	3.44	3.47	Very Effective
6. Using mathematical game-based learning activities enabled my learners/me to comply with the requirements given by me/my teacher, and it developed a willingness to do comply with the task.	3.80	3.72	3.71	3.69	2.59	2.90	3.45	3.42	3.41	Very Effective
7. Mathematical game-based learning activities are easy to manipulate thus it makes the lesson easy for my learners/me to understand.	3.82	3.70	3.92	3.93	2.49	2.87	3.50	3.47	3.46	Very Effective
8. Mathematical game-based learning activities enable my learners/me to review.	3.87	3.76	3.90	3.78	2.97	3.18	3.58	3.42	3.56	Very Effective

9. Mathematical game-based learning activities are effective in learning.	3.81	3.79	3.91	3.85	3.07	3.22	3.64	3.44	3.59	Very Effective
10. My learner/I corrected their/my mistakes when they/I play mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.86	3.83	3.89	3.87	3.24	3.31	3.67	3.49	3.65	Very Effective
Overall Mean	Teacher						3.51		Very Effective	
	Learner						3.53		Very Effective	

Table 9 presents the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of digital games as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under understanding. The overall mean ratings for teachers (3.51) and learners (3.53) both fall within the "Very Effective" category. Kahoot and Quizizz received the highest ratings from both groups, indicating strong approval and perceived effectiveness in learning. Wordwall received the lowest scores, especially from teachers, yet still remained within the "Very Effective" range, suggesting it is beneficial despite lower evaluations. These findings align with Ismail & Mohammad (2017), who noted improved comprehension and problem-solving accuracy when Kahoot and Quizizz were integrated into algebra lessons. Dela Cruz & Torres (2021) found that Wordwall, though less interactive, helped reinforce math definitions and rules. Su & Cheng (2019) highlighted that interactive games improved logical reasoning and mathematical thinking. Overall, Kahoot, Quizizz, and Wordwall are highly effective in enhancing mathematical understanding, promoting retention, participation, and deeper learning.

Table 10
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Digital Games as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Mastery

Statements	Kahoot		Quizizz		Wordwall		Interactive Games		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. Mathematical game-based learning activities promote knowledge retention.	3.84	3.73	3.69	3.54	3.08	3.14	3.79	3.68	3.56	Very Effective
2. Using mathematical game-based learning activities, my learners/I can still remember the concepts or ways to solve problems even after few weeks.	3.67	3.71	3.40	3.43	2.93	2.99	3.44	3.61	3.40	Very Effective

3.	With mathematical game-based learning activities, the topic is retained in my learner's/my mind.	3.84	3.68	3.63	3.26	2.95	2.96	3.67	3.36	3.42	Very Effective
4.	Mathematical game-based learning activities encourage my learner/ me to do self-study and keep the topic refreshed in my learner's/my mind.	3.80	3.72	3.52	3.28	2.87	2.90	3.60	3.47	3.40	Very Effective
5.	The interactive nature of mathematical game-based learning activities can create a long-lasting memory.	3.72	3.68	3.63	3.40	2.82	2.85	3.65	3.56	3.41	Very Effective
6.	Whenever my learners/I engage themselves/myself in these mathematical game-based learning activities, it is much easier for them/me to retain or recall the information.	3.64	3.62	3.59	3.34	2.96	3.00	3.70	3.58	3.43	Very Effective
7.	Mathematical game-based learning activities enabled my learners/me to review.	3.71	3.68	3.65	3.44	3.06	3.09	3.73	3.63	3.50	Very Effective
8.	After using mathematical game-based learning activities, it enabled my learner's/my brain to solve challenging math problems.	3.75	3.75	3.59	3.51	3.09	3.22	3.67	3.53	3.51	Very Effective
9.	Problems are still difficult but now my learners/I can cope up compared to before.	3.66	3.66	3.65	3.49	3.05	3.26	3.75	3.63	3.52	Very Effective
10.	Because of mathematical game-based learning activities, my learners/I still remember something.	3.87	3.85	3.67	3.53	3.24	3.27	3.70	3.58	3.59	Very Effective

Overall Mean	Teacher	3.51	Very Effective
	Learner	3.44	Very Effective

Table 10 shows the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of digital games as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under mastery. The overall mean ratings were 3.51 for teachers and 3.44 for learners, both categorized as "Very Effective." Kahoot consistently received the highest ratings from both teachers and learners, followed by interactive games with high scores. Quizziz showed moderately high effectiveness, while Wordwall received the lowest ratings. These findings support Wang (2015), who found that Kahoot significantly increased learner engagement and long-term content retention. Ismail & Mohammad (2017) also noted that regular use of Kahoot improved learners' mastery of mathematical operations. Bicen & Kocakoyun (2018) compared Kahoot and Quizziz, concluding that both platforms enhanced the recall of mathematical formulas and procedures. Overall, the data and supporting studies confirm that game-based learning tools like Kahoot, Quizziz, and interactive games are highly effective in enhancing mastery and retention of mathematical concepts.

Table 11
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Digital Games as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity

Digital Games	Group	Overall Mean	Qualitative Description
Engagement	Teacher	3.54	Very effective
	Learner	3.58	Very effective
Understanding	Teacher	3.51	Very effective
	Learner	3.53	Very effective
Mastery	Teacher	3.51	Very effective
	Learner	3.44	Very effective

Table 11 presents the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of digital games as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities. The mean ratings, ranging from 3.44 to 3.58, indicate that digital games are "Very Effective" in terms of engagement, understanding, and mastery, as perceived by both teachers and learners. This result is supported by Guan et al. (2022), who highlighted the interactive and immersive nature of games as key drivers of learner engagement in mathematics. Abbott (2019) also emphasized the role of game-based learning in fostering active participation and enthusiasm. Additionally, Anastasiadis et al. (2018) noted that digital game-based learning effectively enhances motivation, engagement, and communication between learners and educators. Game-based learning has been shown to improve concept retention, support teaching efficiency, and enrich the overall learning experience. These findings collectively affirm that digital game-based learning is a highly effective strategy for improving engagement, understanding, and mastery in mathematics.

Table 12
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Mathematical Manipulatives as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Engagement

Statements	Board Games		Geo-Board		Fraction Tiles		Base Ten Blocks		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. My learners/I enjoy doing activities with the use of mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.73	3.67	3.67	3.76	3.65	3.61	3.60	3.58	3.61	Very Effective
2. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to learn.	3.51	3.58	3.51	3.73	3.51	3.60	3.45	3.53	3.58	Very Effective
3. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to attend a class every day.	3.73	3.58	3.73	3.75	3.61	3.53	3.49	3.51	3.58	Very Effective
4. My learners/I like playing mathematical game-based learning activities in class.	3.65	3.48	3.63	3.69	3.51	3.46	3.42	3.49	3.53	Very Effective
5. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to explore mathematics more.	3.63	3.50	3.61	3.65	3.45	3.37	3.45	3.44	3.51	Very Effective
6. Mathematical game-based learning activities make my learners/me attentive and participative in class.	3.65	3.52	3.61	3.64	3.49	3.40	3.36	3.44	3.53	Very Effective
7. Using mathematical game-based learning activities seems interesting to my learners/me.	3.59	3.48	3.65	3.68	3.53	3.46	3.42	3.52	3.57	Very Effective
8. My learners/I enjoy playing mathematical game-based learning activities in class and at the same time my learners/I also learn.	3.69	3.60	3.64	3.71	3.56	3.56	3.47	3.54	3.61	Very Effective
9. Mathematical game-based learning activities	3.73	3.62	3.68	3.73	3.55	3.52	3.53	3.56	3.62	Very Effective

provided my learners/me to participate in the lesson.											
10. Mathematical game-based learning activities increased my learner's/my interest in the lesson.	3.72	3.57	3.64	3.73	3.62	3.58	3.56	3.58	3.63	Very Effective	
Overall Mean	Teacher						3.58		Very Effective		
	Learner						3.57		Very Effective		

Table 12 reveals the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of mathematical manipulatives in mathematical game-based learning activities under engagement. Both teachers and learners rated these activities using manipulatives like board games, geo-boards, fraction circle tiles, and base ten blocks as very effective, with mean ratings of 3.58 for teachers and 3.57 for learners. Geo-boards and board games received the highest ratings, while base ten blocks, though effective, had lower scores. These findings align with Huang & Hew (2018), who noted that game-based learning enhances motivation and engagement through active participation. Ramirez & Salvador (2020) also demonstrated increased engagement using manipulatives in math lessons. Kim & Lee (2016) found geo-boards improved spatial reasoning and engagement, while Fuchs & Karns (2017) highlighted how fraction circle manipulatives helped visualize fractions and increased learner attention. Wilson & Smith (2015) emphasized that base ten blocks support engagement through hands-on exploration of number concepts. These studies confirm that manipulatives in game-based learning are highly effective for engaging learners in mathematics.

Table 13
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Mathematical Manipulatives as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Understanding

Statements	Board Games		Geo-Board		Fraction Circle Tiles		Base Ten Blocks		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. Mathematical game-based learning activities help my learners/me easily understand some parts of the lesson.	3.59	3.68	3.40	3.61	3.49	3.58	3.43	3.60	3.55	Very Effective
2. My learners/I think mathematical game-based learning activities are important and useful	3.56	3.67	3.39	3.52	3.40	3.57	3.36	3.60	3.51	Very Effective

	for better learning.										
3.	My learners/I learn in mathematics because of mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.53	3.62	3.36	3.50	3.40	3.55	3.31	3.60	3.48	Very Effective
4.	Mathematical game-based learning activities help my learners/me to enhance their/my social skills.	3.49	3.56	3.32	3.45	3.31	3.50	3.24	3.53	3.43	Very Effective
5.	My learners/I learn mathematics concepts easily because of mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.50	3.59	3.15	3.36	3.18	3.43	3.19	3.54	3.37	Very Effective
6.	Using mathematical game-based learning activities enabled my learners/me to comply with the requirements given by me/my teacher, and it developed a willingness to do comply with the task.	3.31	3.51	3.17	3.42	3.28	3.45	3.16	3.56	3.36	Very Effective
7.	Mathematical game-based learning activities are easy to manipulate thus it makes the lesson easy for my learners/me to understand.	3.27	3.53	3.31	3.48	3.35	3.55	3.24	3.61	3.42	Very Effective
8.	Mathematical game-based learning activities enable my	3.41	3.63	3.37	3.56	3.47	3.60	3.25	3.60	3.49	Very Effective

learners/me to review.										
9. Mathematical game-based learning activities are effective in learning.	3.50	3.67	3.42	3.59	3.48	3.58	3.30	3.60	3.52	Very Effective
10. My learner/I corrected their/my mistakes when they/I play mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.50	3.63	3.42	3.62	3.49	3.58	3.31	3.62	3.52	Very Effective
Overall Mean	Teacher						3.37		Very Effective	
	Learner						3.56		Very Effective	

Table 13 depicts the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of mathematical manipulatives in mathematical game-based learning activities under understanding. Both teachers and learners rated these activities as very effective, with mean ratings of 3.56 for teachers and 3.37 for learners. Board games received the highest ratings, particularly in supporting understanding and engagement. In contrast, base ten blocks and geo-boards received the lowest ratings, though all tools were still rated as "Very Effective," reflecting their positive impact on math instruction. The findings align with Carbonneau et al. (2013), who found that manipulatives like base ten blocks and fraction tiles significantly improved understanding compared to traditional instruction. Boaler (2016) emphasized that game-based, manipulative-rich environments foster deeper understanding by encouraging exploration and visual representation. Similarly, Moyer-Packenham & Westenskow (2013) noted that both virtual and physical manipulatives enhance conceptual understanding, especially with guided instruction. These studies confirm the value of manipulatives in promoting deeper comprehension in mathematics.

Table 14
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Mathematical Manipulatives as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Mastery

Statements	Board Games		Geo-Board		Fraction Circle Tiles		Base Ten Blocks		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. Mathematical game-based learning activities promote knowledge retention.	3.61	3.60	3.62	3.66	3.46	3.52	3.57	3.56	3.58	Very Effective
2. Using mathematical game-based learning activities, my learners/I can still remember the concepts or ways to solve problems	3.33	3.57	3.41	3.60	3.32	3.59	3.40	3.58	3.48	Very Effective

	even after few weeks.										
3.	With mathematical game-based learning activities, the topic is retained in my learner's/my mind.	3.51	3.53	3.56	3.54	3.38	3.44	3.53	3.46	3.49	Very Effective
4.	Mathematical game-based learning activities encourage my learner/ me to do self-study and keep the topic refreshed in my learner's/my mind.	3.46	3.39	3.52	3.44	3.28	3.42	3.46	3.40	3.42	Very Effective
5.	The interactive nature of mathematical game-based learning activities can create a long-lasting memory.	3.49	3.40	3.57	3.51	3.22	3.36	3.40	3.36	3.41	Very Effective
6.	Whenever my learners/I engage themselves/myself in these mathematical game-based learning activities, it is much easier for them/me to retain or recall the information.	3.47	3.36	3.52	3.47	3.36	3.45	3.49	3.45	3.45	Very Effective
7.	Mathematical game-based learning activities enabled my learners/me to review.	3.47	3.40	3.58	3.58	3.32	3.43	3.48	3.45	3.46	Very Effective
8.	After using mathematical game-based learning activities, it enabled my learner's/my brain to solve challenging math problems.	3.52	3.51	3.57	3.56	3.53	3.63	3.58	3.56	3.56	Very Effective
9.	Problems are still difficult but now my learners/I can cope up compared to before.	3.65	3.63	3.57	3.58	3.55	3.55	3.60	3.59	3.59	Very Effective
10.	Because of mathematical game-based learning activities, my learners/I still	3.67	3.64	3.58	3.64	3.64	3.65	3.65	3.65	3.64	Very Effective

remember something.										
Overall Mean	Teacher						3.50		Very Effective	
	Learner						3.52		Very Effective	

Table 14 reveals the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of mathematical manipulatives in mathematical game-based learning activities under mastery. Both teachers and learners rated all four manipulatives—Geo-Boards, Board Games, Base Ten Blocks, and Fraction Circle Tiles—as very effective, with mean ratings of 3.50 for teachers and 3.52 for learners. Geo-Boards received the highest ratings, followed closely by Board Games, while Base Ten Blocks and Fraction Circle Tiles, though still rated as very effective, scored slightly lower. These findings are supported by Sarama & Clements (2016), who found that manipulatives like Geo-Boards promoted mastery in early geometry and measurement skills. Bicer & Capraro (2017) also noted that manipulatives like Base Ten Blocks and Fraction Tiles enhanced mastery in solving multi-step word problems by providing concrete support for abstract thinking. These studies affirm that manipulative- and game-based learning environments are crucial in fostering deeper learning and long-term mastery in mathematics.

Table 15
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Mathematical Manipulatives as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity

Mathematical Manipulatives	Group	Overall Mean	Qualitative Description
Engagement	Teacher	3.58	Very effective
	Learner	3.57	Very effective
Understanding	Teacher	3.37	Very effective
	Learner	3.56	Very effective
Mastery	Teacher	3.50	Very effective
	Learner	3.52	Very effective

Table 15 reveals the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of mathematical manipulatives as mathematical game-based learning activities. The mean ratings, ranging from 3.50 to 3.58, indicate that mathematical manipulatives are considered very effective in terms of engagement, understanding, and mastery by both teachers and learners. These findings align with McCarthy and Pisano (2023), who argue that manipulatives are effective because they present concepts in multiple ways, are multisensory, and promote communication—key factors in developing a deep understanding. By interacting with manipulatives, learners can creatively solve problems, make connections between abstract concepts and real-world situations, and gain a deeper understanding. These studies affirm that manipulatives help create an active, engaging learning environment, encouraging exploration, discussion, and application, ultimately supporting long-term mastery of mathematical skills and concepts.

Table 16
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Cooperative Learning as
Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Engagement

Statements	Group Problem-Solving		Think-Pair-Share		Cooperative Quizzes		Jigsaw-Puzzle Activity		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. My learners/I enjoy doing activities with the use of mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.61	3.65	3.68	3.63	3.62	3.64	3.05	3.15	3.50	Very Effective
2. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to learn.	3.31	3.64	3.40	3.62	3.36	3.63	3.09	3.17	3.40	Very Effective
3. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to attend a class every day.	3.67	3.64	3.73	3.61	3.68	3.62	2.80	2.88	3.45	Very Effective
4. My learners/I like playing mathematical game-based learning activities in class.	3.56	3.64	3.65	3.60	3.66	3.62	2.63	2.73	3.39	Very Effective
5. Mathematical game-based learning activities motivate my learners/me to explore mathematics more.	3.58	3.65	3.63	3.62	3.63	3.64	2.54	2.60	3.36	Very Effective
6. Mathematical game-based learning activities make my learners/me attentive and participative in class.	3.62	3.65	3.73	3.63	3.66	3.64	2.80	2.91	3.46	Very Effective
7. Using mathematical game-based learning activities seems interesting to my learners/me.	3.61	3.61	3.68	3.58	3.66	3.60	2.72	2.83	3.41	Very Effective
8. My learners/I enjoy playing mathematical game-based learning activities in class and at the same time my learners/I also learn.	3.64	3.61	3.73	3.60	3.68	3.60	3.11	3.19	3.52	Very Effective
9. Mathematical game-based learning activities	3.62	3.64	3.72	3.61	3.65	3.63	3.14	3.21	3.53	Very Effective

provided my learners/me to participate in the lesson.											
10. Mathematical game-based learning activities increased my learner's/my interest in the lesson.	3.61	3.65	3.74	3.63	3.65	3.65	3.29	3.39	3.58	Very Effective	
Overall Mean	Teacher						3.45		Very Effective		
	Learner						3.47		Very Effective		

Table 16 reveals the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of cooperative learning in mathematical game-based learning activities under engagement. The data shows that these activities, when combined with cooperative learning strategies, are perceived as very effective by both teachers (3.45) and learners (3.47). Among the strategies, Think-Pair-Share received the highest ratings, followed by Group Problem-Solving and Cooperative Quizzes, while the Jigsaw-Puzzle Activity, though still effective, received slightly lower ratings. These findings align with Gillies (2016), who found that cooperative learning strategies like Think-Pair-Share and Jigsaw promoted higher engagement, improved problem-solving skills, and deeper understanding of math concepts. However, the results contrast with Hernández-Gantes & Riera (2019), who noted that the effectiveness of the Jigsaw strategy depends on clear task design and learner readiness. This suggests that careful planning and support from teachers are essential for maximizing the benefits of cooperative learning in mathematics. Overall, the study supports the value of integrating cooperative learning strategies in game-based learning to enhance motivation, participation, and learning effectiveness.

Table 17
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Cooperative Learning as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Understanding

Statements	Group Problem-Solving		Think-Pair-Share		Cooperative Quizzes		Jigsaw-Puzzle Activity		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. Mathematical game-based learning activities help my learners/me easily understand some parts of the lesson.	3.65	3.48	3.53	3.52	3.59	3.56	3.05	3.26	3.46	Very Effective
2. My learners/I think mathematical game-based learning activities are important and useful for better leaning.	3.39	3.49	3.40	3.53	3.37	3.57	3.13	3.31	3.40	Very Effective
3. My learners/I learn in mathematics because of	3.71	3.47	3.64	3.47	3.62	3.54	2.77	3.01	3.40	Very Effective

	mathematical game-based learning activities.										
4.	Mathematical game-based learning activities help my learners/me to enhance their/my social skills.	3.63	3.46	3.58	3.42	3.55	3.53	2.58	2.84	3.32	Very Effective
5.	My learners/I learn mathematics concepts easily because of mathematical game-based learning activities.	3.60	3.49	3.54	3.38	3.51	3.53	2.43	2.71	3.27	Very Effective
6.	Using mathematical game-based learning activities enabled my learners/me to comply with the requirements given by me/my teacher, and it developed a willingness to do comply with the task.	3.62	3.47	3.59	3.46	3.58	3.54	2.76	3.03	3.38	Very Effective
7.	Mathematical game-based learning activities are easy to manipulate thus it makes the lesson easy for my learners/me to understand.	3.55	3.46	3.57	3.41	3.53	3.52	2.71	2.90	3.33	Very Effective
8.	Mathematical game-based learning activities enable my learners/me to review.	3.59	3.46	3.62	3.50	3.58	3.54	3.13	3.31	3.47	Very Effective
9.	Mathematical game-based learning activities are effective in learning.	3.61	3.48	3.63	3.54	3.60	3.58	3.23	3.32	3.50	Very Effective
10.	My learner/I corrected their/my mistakes	3.61	3.48	3.62	3.58	3.63	3.59	3.43	3.51	3.56	Very Effective

when they/ play mathematical game-based learning activities.										
Overall Mean	Teacher						3.41		Very Effective	
	Learner						3.41		Very Effective	

Table 17 reveals the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of cooperative learning in mathematical game-based learning activities under understanding. The data indicates that both teachers (3.41) and learners (3.41) perceive these activities as very effective in supporting various aspects of mathematics education. Among the cooperative strategies, Group Problem-Solving, Think-Pair-Share, and Cooperative Quizzes received higher ratings, ranging from 3.39 to 3.71. While the Jigsaw-Puzzle Activity received comparatively lower ratings (ranging from 2.43 to 3.51), it still fell within the “Very Effective” range. These findings align with Gillies (2016), who noted that cooperative strategies like Think-Pair-Share and Group Problem-Solving enhance understanding by promoting discussion, peer teaching, and explanation. Mahmoud (2018) further emphasized that Think-Pair-Share improves comprehension by encouraging learners to verbalize their thinking, reinforcing conceptual understanding. Olanrewaju & Adewale (2020) affirmed that cooperative quizzes improved comprehension through peer collaboration, leading to better mastery and fewer misconceptions. Overall, these studies underscore the effectiveness of cooperative learning strategies in fostering deep mathematical understanding.

Table 18
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Cooperative Learning as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity under Mastery

Statements	Group Problem-Solving		Think-Pair-Share		Cooperative Quizzes		Jigsaw-Puzzle Activity		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner	Teacher	Learner		
1. Mathematical game-based learning activities promote knowledge retention.	3.63	3.78	3.53	3.80	3.62	3.69	3.08	3.11	3.53	Very Effective
2. Using mathematical game-based learning activities, my learners/I can still remember the concepts or ways to solve problems even after few weeks.	3.31	3.77	3.24	3.79	3.27	3.71	2.91	2.98	3.37	Very Effective
3. With mathematical game-based learning activities, the topic is retained in my learner's/my mind.	3.56	3.76	3.44	3.76	3.51	3.68	2.67	2.69	3.38	Very Effective

4. Mathematical game-based learning activities encourage my learner/ me to do self-study and keep the topic refreshed in my learner's/my mind.	3.50	3.75	3.38	3.75	3.44	3.67	2.46	2.49	3.31	Very Effective
5. The interactive nature of mathematical game-based learning activities can create a long-lasting memory.	3.49	3.75	3.33	3.75	3.41	3.66	2.31	2.34	3.26	Very Effective
6. Whenever my learners/I engage themselves/myself in these mathematical game-based learning activities, it is much easier for them/me to retain or recall the information.	3.59	3.77	3.44	3.76	3.47	3.67	2.73	2.77	3.40	Very Effective
7. Mathematical game-based learning activities enabled my learners/me to review.	3.61	3.69	3.46	3.71	3.51	3.64	2.48	2.52	3.33	Very Effective
8. After using mathematical game-based learning activities, it enabled my learner's/my brain to solve challenging math problems.	3.64	3.72	3.52	3.72	3.55	3.66	2.85	2.89	3.44	Very Effective
9. Problems are still difficult but now my learners/I can cope up compared to before.	3.63	3.75	3.53	3.79	3.60	3.72	2.89	2.93	3.48	Very Effective
10. Because of mathematical game-based learning activities, my learners/I still remember something.	3.66	3.77	3.56	3.80	3.63	3.73	3.12	3.15	3.55	Very Effective
Overall Mean	Teacher						3.31			Very Effective
	Learner						3.50			Very Effective

Table 18 reveals the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of cooperative learning in mathematical game-based learning activities under mastery. The data shows that both teachers (3.31) and learners (3.50) perceive these activities as very effective in enhancing knowledge retention and conceptual understanding. Among the cooperative

strategies, Group Problem-Solving, Think-Pair-Share, and Cooperative Quizzes consistently received higher ratings, while Jigsaw-Puzzle Activities, though rated lower, still fell within the "Very Effective" range. Research supports that cooperative learning strategies, such as Think-Pair-Share, cooperative quizzes, and Jigsaw activities, improve mastery by engaging learners, fostering teamwork, and reinforcing learning. Mahmoud (2018) found that Think-Pair-Share enhances problem-solving skills through verbalization and peer discussion. Olanrewaju & Adewale (2020) affirmed that cooperative quizzes improve mastery by allowing learners to engage, explain, and correct misunderstandings. Aronson & Bridgeman (2020) highlighted that Jigsaw activities promote interdependence, deepening understanding and retention. Overall, these strategies significantly enhance learners' mastery of mathematical concepts.

Table 19
Perception of the Respondents on the Effectiveness of Cooperative Learning as Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activity

Cooperative Learning	Group	Overall Mean	Qualitative Description
Engagement	Teacher	3.45	Very effective
	Learner	3.47	Very effective
Understanding	Teacher	3.41	Very effective
	Learner	3.41	Very effective
Mastery	Teacher	3.31	Very effective
	Learner	3.50	Very effective

Table 19 reveals the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of cooperative learning in mathematical game-based learning activities. The mean ratings, ranging from 3.31 to 3.50, indicate that cooperative learning is considered very effective in terms of engagement, understanding, and mastery by both teachers and learners. Research consistently shows that cooperative learning strategies significantly enhance students' engagement, understanding, and mastery in mathematics. Slavin (2014) synthesizes evidence that these strategies positively impact all three areas by combining social interaction with individual accountability, fostering meaningful learning. Ugiagbe (2025) further affirms the positive shift in learners' attitudes when using cooperative learning compared to traditional methods. Johnson & Holubec (2013) highlight how cooperative learning increases engagement through positive interdependence and active participation, creating a supportive social environment that motivates learners. Overall, these studies confirm the crucial role of cooperative learning strategies in improving academic outcomes and fostering positive attitudes toward mathematics.

Table 20
Summary on the Perception of Respondents on the Effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities

Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities	Group	Grand Mean	Qualitative Description
Digital Games	Teacher	3.52	Very Effective
	Learner	3.52	Very Effective

Mathematical Manipulatives	Teacher	3.48	Very Effective
	Learner	3.53	Very Effective
Cooperative Learning	Teacher	3.39	Very Effective
	Learner	3.46	Very Effective

Table 20 summarizes the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities. The data shows a very positive overall perception from both teachers and learners, as reflected in their consistently high ratings across all categories. Digital games received the highest ratings, with a grand mean of 3.52 from both groups, indicating they are viewed as very effective in supporting math learning. Mathematical manipulatives followed closely, with teachers rating them at 3.48 and learners at 3.53, both within the very effective range. Cooperative learning strategies, while rated slightly lower, still received favorable ratings, with a grand mean of 3.39 from teachers and 3.46 from learners, maintaining a "very effective" qualitative description. These findings suggest that all three approaches—digital games, mathematical manipulatives, and cooperative learning strategies—are well-received, with digital games and manipulatives being perceived as slightly more impactful.

3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents on the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities?

Table 21
Significant Difference in the Perception of Respondents on the Effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities

Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities	Group	Mean	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
Digital Games	Learner	3.50	.40	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher	3.54			
Mathematical Manipulatives	Learner	3.45	.14	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher	3.48			
Cooperative Learning	Learner	3.39	.96	Accept Ho	Not Significant
	Teacher	3.39			

Table 21 reveals the significant difference in the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities using the Analysis of Variance (F-test) at the 0.05 level of significance. The F-values for Digital Games, Mathematical Manipulatives, and Cooperative Learning activities were all greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates that there was no significant difference in the perception of the effectiveness of these activities. Both teachers and learners shared similar views on the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities. Supporting this, Sabirli and Coklar (2020) found that digital educational games enhance learners' access to lessons, resulting in improved academic performance. Sapin (2022) also highlighted that game-based learning positively influences students' attitudes toward mathematics, boosting motivation and long-term memory retention. The lack of significant difference in perceptions can be attributed to

both teachers and learners experiencing the same positive outcomes from these activities, leading to aligned, favorable evaluations.

4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents when grouped according to profile?

Table 22
Significant Difference in the Perception of Teachers When Grouped According to Profile

Profile	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
Type of school	.399	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Level of Training Attended	Statistic cannot be computed	None	Constant
Educational Attainment	.619	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Position	.392	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 22 highlights the significant difference in the perception of teachers when grouped according to profile using the Analysis of Variance (F-test) at the 0.05 level of significance. The F-values for all profiles, except for the Level of Training Attended, were greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates no significant difference in the perceptions of teacher-respondents when grouped by Type of School, Educational Attainment, and Position. Since all teachers attended training at the division level only, the significance difference in perceptions based on training level could not be determined. The results suggest that the Type of School, Educational Attainment, and Position do not influence teachers' perceptions of the effectiveness of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities. The lack of significant difference is likely due to shared professional contexts, as teachers follow the same curriculum, use similar teaching strategies, and have attended similar training programs, leading to aligned perceptions across all groups.

Table 23
Significant Difference in the Perception of Learners When Grouped According to Profile

Profile	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
Type of School	.849	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Available Learning Materials	.004	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 23 reveals the significant difference in the perception of learners when grouped according to profile using the Analysis of Variance (F-test) at the 0.05 level of significance. The F-value for the profile Type of School was greater than 0.05, leading to

the acceptance of the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating no significant difference in perceptions based on the type of school. However, for the profile of available learning materials at home, the F-value was less than 0.05, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating a significant difference in learners' perceptions based on the availability of learning resources. These results suggest that the type of school does not influence learners' perceptions of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities. However, the availability of learning materials at home plays a significant role in shaping their perceptions. Learners believe that having more learning materials positively impacts their engagement and effectiveness in game-based learning activities. This aligns with Dichev & Dicheva (2017), who found that access to digital materials, like tablets or laptops, improves learners' performance in digital game-based learning.

5. How serious are the challenges encountered by the teachers on the use of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities?

Table 24
Challenges Encountered by Teachers on the Use of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under Curriculum Integration

Challenges on Curriculum Integration	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Difficulty aligning games with learning objectives.	3.70	Very Serious
2. Creating a gaming atmosphere that is adapted to all the learner's ability.	3.48	Very Serious
3. Inadequate time for instruction of using game.	3.43	Very Serious
4. The cost associated with developing a game.	3.35	Very Serious
5. Combining engaging games with achieving the curriculum.	3.48	Very Serious
6. Unstructured lessons that did not go along with the curriculum.	3.39	Very Serious
7. Clear presentation of what students are learning.	3.35	Very Serious
8. Lack of time for lesson preparation using GBL.	3.61	Very Serious
9. Balancing game-based learning with other teaching method.	3.48	Very Serious
10. Difficulty in choosing the right game that aligns with the goal.	3.61	Very Serious

Table 24 shows the challenges encountered by teachers in using Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under curriculum integration. The data reveals several challenges, with the most significant being aligning games with learning goals, which received the highest mean of 3.70. Time constraints, particularly in lesson preparation and selecting appropriate games, also emerged as major issues, with a mean of 3.61. Other challenges include making games suitable for all students, balancing games with other teaching methods, and ensuring games meet curriculum goals, all with a mean of 3.48. Teachers also reported difficulties with the cost of making games, lessons not fitting the curriculum well, and struggling to explain learning objectives, with respective means of 3.35 and 3.39. Overall, the data highlights the need for more support, time, and

resources for effective game-based teaching. Research supports these findings, with Plass et al. (2015) and Papadakis et al. (2018) noting that many available games are not aligned with curriculum standards. Jong & Shang (2015) emphasize time constraints due to insufficient institutional support, while Wouters & Van Oostendorp (2017) highlight difficulties in adapting games for diverse learners. These studies underscore the importance of aligned, accessible, and adaptable game-based learning tools to enhance teaching effectiveness.

Table 25
Challenges Encountered by Teachers on the Use of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under Technological and Logical

Challenges on Technological and Logical	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Inadequate gaming materials such as software, hardware, slide, and boards among others.	3.39	Very Serious
2. Lack of Learning Resources (Internet, Computers, Cellphones, Mathematical Manipulatives).	3.30	Very Serious
3. Large class size.	3.22	Serious
4. Inadequate space for game.	3.00	Serious
5. Unpredictable duration of applying and participating in GBL.	3.00	Serious
6. Teacher's negative feelings towards using games in the classroom.	2.91	Serious
7. Teacher's behaviour management.	3.04	Serious
8. Lack of confidence in my ability to use game-based learning tools.	3.17	Serious
9. Lack of logical strategies to integrate motivation.	3.26	Very Serious
10. High speed Internet access.	3.22	Serious

Table 25 reveals that teachers face significant challenges when using Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities due to technological and logistical factors. The most notable issues include a lack of gaming materials, such as software and hardware (mean of 3.39), and insufficient resources like internet and computers (mean of 3.30). Teachers also struggle with maintaining student motivation during games (mean of 3.26), managing large class sizes (mean of 3.22), and limited space for games (mean of 3.00). Other challenges include negative feelings toward using games (mean of 2.91) and lack of confidence with game tools (mean of 3.17). These results highlight the need for improved materials, support, and teacher training. Studies by Padakis et al. (2018), Huang et al. (2020), Zheng et al. (2016), and others emphasize the importance of addressing these barriers to successfully integrate game-based learning and ensure effective teaching.

Table 26
Challenges Encountered by Teachers on the Use of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under Teacher Training

Challenges on Teacher Training	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Lack of pedagogical.	3.09	Serious

2. Lack of teacher's knowledge or proficiency in the use of game.	3.13	Serious
3. Fear of failure as knowledge authority.	3.30	Very Serious
4. Lack of training or knowledge on how to use GBL.	3.17	Serious
5. Low administrative or parental support.	3.13	Serious
6. Lack of opportunity to attend trainings.	3.26	Very Serious
7. Inconsistent implementation of GBL.	3.13	Serious
8. Lack of effective assessment.	3.17	Serious
9. Overlooking diverse learning.	3.30	Very Serious
10. Lack of financial support.	3.17	Serious

Table 26 reveals the challenges teachers face when using Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities, particularly in teacher training. The data shows that all challenges are perceived as serious or very serious, with mean scores ranging from 3.09 to 3.30. The highest-rated challenges include fear of failure as a knowledge authority (mean of 3.30), overlooking diverse learning needs (mean of 3.30), and lack of opportunities for training (mean of 3.26), highlighting concerns about teacher confidence, inclusivity, and professional development. Other challenges include lack of pedagogical knowledge (mean of 3.09) and limited proficiency in using games (mean of 3.13). These findings align with studies by Yusoff et al. (2015), Bakar et al. (2019), and Siew et al. (2017), which emphasize the need for more training, funding, and access to professional development to help teachers overcome these barriers and effectively integrate game-based learning into their lessons.

Table 27
Challenges Encountered by Teachers on the Use of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under Technological Competence

Challenges on Technological Competence	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Difficulty in Integrating Games with existing tools.	2.96	Serious
2. Limited access to technology.	2.91	Serious
3. Lack of technical skills.	3.09	Serious
4. Limited access to quality platforms.	3.09	Serious
5. Limited familiarity with GBL.	2.83	Serious
6. Difficulty in troubleshooting.	2.78	Serious
7. Rapid pace of technological advancement.	2.96	Serious
8. Struggle in modifying instructional design.	2.83	Serious
9. Balancing technological demand with workload.	2.91	Serious
10. Addressing varied levels of student's technological proficiency.	2.87	Serious

Table 27 reveals the challenges teachers encounter when using Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities under technological competence. The data shows that all challenges are rated as serious, with mean scores ranging from 2.78 to 3.09. The most pressing issues are a lack of technical skills and limited access to quality platforms, both scoring 3.09. Teachers also face difficulties integrating games with existing tools (mean

of 2.96), limited access to technology (mean of 2.91), and balancing technological demands with their workload (mean of 2.91). Other challenges include limited familiarity with Game-Based Learning (mean of 2.83), troubleshooting issues (mean of 2.78), adapting instructional design (mean of 2.83), and rapid technological advancements (mean of 2.96).

These findings align with Zhao et al. (2021), Lin et al. (2021), and Mouza et al. (2016), who highlighted the barriers of limited technical skills, lack of professional development, and insufficient technological support. Ifenthaler & Schweinbenz (2016) and Hwang et al. (2019) emphasize that rapid technological changes and workload management add to these challenges. In summary, teachers often lack the technical skills and resources to integrate game-based learning effectively, and the fast pace of technological advancements makes it harder to keep up, adding stress to their work.

Table 28
Summary of the Challenges Encountered by Teacher on the Use of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities

Challenges	Mean	Qualitative Description
Curriculum Integration	3.49	Very serious
Technological and Logical	3.15	Serious
Teacher Training	3.19	Serious
Technological Competence	2.92	Serious

Table 28 reveals that the most significant challenge teachers face in using Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities is curriculum integration, with a mean of 3.49, indicating it is very serious. This highlights concerns about aligning games with learning objectives and instructional time. Teacher training (mean of 3.19) and technological and logistical challenges (mean of 3.15) are also considered serious, emphasizing gaps in professional development, support, and access to effective tools. Technological competence scored the lowest at 2.92, still rated serious, reflecting ongoing issues with skills and confidence in using technology. These findings are supported by Rahma and Absharini (2024), who noted that effective curriculum design for the digital age requires aligning technology with learning objectives. Mpolomoka et al. (2023) emphasized that integrating digital tools addresses accessibility challenges and enhances the educational experience. Yuyun (2018) highlighted the importance of professional development in helping teachers integrate technology, emphasizing the alignment of technology with curriculum goals to ensure effective and relevant teaching practices.

6. Is there a significant difference on the challenges encountered by teachers when grouped according to profile?

Table 29
Significant Difference on the Challenges Encountered by Teachers when grouped according to Profile

Profile	Significance <i>F</i>	Decision	Remarks
Type of School	.923	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Level of Training Attended	Statistic cannot be computed	None	Constant
Educational Qualifications	.415	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Teaching Position	.063	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 29 reveals the significant difference in the challenges encountered by teachers when grouped according to profile using the Analysis of Variance (F-test) at the 0.05 level of significance. The F-values for all profiles, except for the Level of Training Attended, are greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho). This indicates no significant difference in the challenges teachers face when grouped by Type of School, Educational Qualifications, and Teaching Position. The Level of Training Attended did not show a significant difference because all respondents attended training at the school, district, and division levels. The results suggest that the Type of School, Educational Qualifications, and Position do not significantly affect the challenges teachers encounter in their teaching process. Therefore, these variables do not impact the utilization of Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities in their teaching practices when grouped by profile.

7. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived effectiveness of the Game-Based Learning Activities and the challenges encountered by teachers?

Table 30
Significant Relationship Between the Perceived Effectiveness of the Game-Based Learning Activities and the Challenges Encountered by Teachers

Group	Significance <i>r</i>	Decision	Remarks
Perceived Effectiveness of the Game-Based Learning Activities	.027	Reject Ho	There is Significant Relationship
Challenges Encountered			

Table 30 reveals a significant relationship between the perceived effectiveness of Game-Based Learning Activities and the challenges encountered by teachers, as determined by Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation r-test at the 0.05 level of significance. The r-value was less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating a statistically significant relationship. This suggests that the effectiveness of Game-Based Learning Activities is closely correlated with the challenges teachers face. It can be inferred that the challenges encountered by teachers may drive more effective teaching strategies, stimulating greater interest among learners and motivating teachers to develop a variety of Game-Based Learning Activities to enhance their teaching methods.

Conclusions

The study showed that most learners and teachers came from small schools. Learners had full access to mathematical manipulatives, but fewer had access to digital tools like cellphones, internet, and laptops. Most teachers had pursued or completed graduate studies and held mid-level or higher teaching positions.

Both teachers and learners found Mathematical Game-Based Learning Activities to be very effective in improving engagement, understanding, and mastery in mathematics. Teachers also encountered several challenges in using game-based learning, with curriculum integration identified as the most serious. Other challenges included limited training, technological issues, and lack of confidence in using digital tools. These challenges were consistent regardless of the teachers' background.

Overall, the study highlights the positive impact of game-based learning in mathematics and the need for better support and resources for teachers to address the challenges they face.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions formulated, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Curriculum planners should consider integrating game-based strategies into the official curriculum by developing guides, resources, and assessment tools that support game-based instruction. Additionally, curriculum planners should ensure that teacher training programs include modules on the design, implementation, and evaluation of contextualized mathematical games, promoting consistency and effectiveness in classroom application.
2. Administrators should support the integration of game-based learning by providing resources, scheduling time for teacher training, and promoting a school culture that values innovative teaching strategies.
3. Teachers are encouraged to incorporate mathematical game-based learning activities into their daily lessons to make mathematics more engaging and accessible. These games should be contextualized to align with learners' local experiences, interests, and learning levels.

4. Teachers should also undergo regular training on designing and implementing effective game-based strategies to ensure meaningful learning outcomes.
5. Teachers should take advantage of existing materials such as manipulatives, flashcards, board games, digital apps, and printed worksheets, adapting them to reflect real-life situations familiar to learners.
6. Teachers should incorporate mathematical game-based learning activities as a regular part of instruction to improve learners' engagement, motivation, and understanding of mathematical concepts.
7. Teachers should use the Contextualized Teaching Strategy Plan to make Mathematical Game-Based Learning more effective. By connecting lessons to learners' real-life experiences and available resources, teachers can improve engagement, understanding, and mastery.
8. Learners should actively participate in game-based learning activities to improve their problem-solving skills, critical thinking, enjoyment, understanding and mastery of mathematics.
9. Parents are encouraged to support game-based learning at home by allowing children to access educational games and engaging with them in playful math-related activities especially using digital learning materials.
10. Future researchers should explore the long-term effects of game-based learning on mathematical performance and investigate its impact across different grade levels, learning abilities, and cultural settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical guidelines to ensure the protection and well-being of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all teacher and learner respondents, with clear and comprehensive information provided about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Parental consent was also secured for learner respondents, ensuring that participation was voluntary and participants could withdraw at any time without consequence. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing all personal data collected, which was securely stored and accessible only to the research team. Participants' rights, dignity, and autonomy were respected throughout the study, and no individual was coerced into participation. The study ensured that all procedures were non-harmful and intended to enhance the learning experience, with the use of digital tools and game-based learning methods specifically designed to improve engagement and outcomes. Data integrity was a priority, and the findings were honestly and transparently reported, with any limitations clearly acknowledged. The research received approval from the relevant ethical review board or academic institution, ensuring full compliance with ethical standards.

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